

A study on volumetric and compressibility properties of some lithium salts in tetrahydrofuran at 298.15 K

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Abstract : Apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) and apparent molar adiabatic compressibilities (ϕ_K) have been determined for solutions of some lithium salts (LiCl, LiBr, LiClO₄ and LiBF₄) in tetrahydrofuran at 298.15 K from density and sound velocity measurements. V_ϕ^0 and ϕ_K^0 of the salts have been obtained from $V_\phi - \sqrt{C}$ and $\phi_K - \sqrt{C}$ data. The data have been quantitatively explained in terms of ion-solvent and ion-ion interactions.

Keywords : Apparent molar volumes, apparent molar adiabatic compressibilities, lithium salts,

Introduction

Recently some workers¹⁻³ have investigated the solvation of some lithium salts dissolved in propylene carbonate or ethylene carbonate based mixed solvents. The salts studied include LiClO₄, LiBr and LiBF₄. However, no studies seem to have been undertaken with regard to volumetric and compressibility properties of LiCl, LiBr, LiClO₄ and LiBF₄ in tetrahydrofuran. Hence, the title study has been undertaken.

Results and discussion

The apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) were calculated from the densities of the solutions using the equation,

$$V_\phi = M/\rho_0 - 1000(\rho - \rho_0)/C\rho_0 \quad (1)$$

where, C is the molarity of the electrolyte solution, M is the molecular weight of the solute and ρ and ρ_0 are the densities of the solution and solvent respectively.

The molar concentrations, densities and the apparent molar volumes of the various electrolyte solutions in THF at 298.15 K are given in Table 1.

From the $V_\phi - C$ data, V_ϕ versus \sqrt{C} curves have been drawn and the plots were found to be linear in all the cases. Masson's equation⁴,

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^0 + S_v \times \sqrt{C} \quad (2)$$

is applicable at this temperature and concentration range studied. The limiting apparent molar volumes, V_ϕ^0 (equal

to partial molar volumes at infinite dilution, $V_\phi^0 = V_2^0$) are obtained by the least squares fitting of $V_\phi - C$ data to the above equation and values of V_ϕ^0 and S_v have been reported in Table 2.

From Table 2, it is seen that the S_v values are positive for all the lithium salts in THF, indicating appreciable ion-ion interactions in this solvent. The V_ϕ^0 values are also large and positive and increase with increase in size of the anions. This is in agreement with earlier findings in several non-aqueous solvents¹⁻⁵.

Adiabatic compressibility coefficients, β were derived from the relation,

$$\beta = \frac{1}{u^2\rho} \quad (3)$$

where ρ the solution density and u is sound velocity in the solution.

The apparent molar isentropic compressibility (ϕ_K) of salt solutions was calculated from the relation,

$$\phi_K = \frac{1000}{C\rho_0} (\beta\rho_0 - \beta_0\rho) + \beta \frac{M}{\rho_0} \quad (4)$$

where, β_0 and β are the compressibility coefficients of the solvent and solution respectively. The molar concentration (C), density (ρ), adiabatic compressibility coefficient (β) and apparent molar adiabatic compressibility

Table 1. Molar concentration (C), density (ρ), apparent molar volume (V_ϕ), ultrasonic sound velocity (u), adiabatic compressibility (β) and apparent molar adiabatic compressibility (ϕ_K) of the lithium salts in tetrahydrofuran (THF) at 298.15 K

C (mol dm ⁻³)	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	V_ϕ (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	u (cm s ⁻¹)	$\beta \times 10^{12}$ (cm ² dyne ⁻¹)	$\phi_K \times 10^{10}$ (cm ³ mol ⁻¹ bar ⁻¹)
LiCl					
0.00000	0.88240	–	128146	69.01	–
0.02165	0.88312	10.42	128193	68.90	–42.49
0.04113	0.88374	11.08	128237	68.81	–41.55
0.05629	0.88421	11.51	128271	68.74	–40.97
0.06928	0.88462	11.78	128298	68.67	–40.52
0.08660	0.88514	12.14	128337	68.59	–39.99
0.10825	0.88579	12.54	128385	68.49	–39.41
LiBr					
0.00000	0.88233	–	128146	69.02	–
0.02348	0.88411	12.38	128160	68.86	–56.84
0.04462	0.88568	13.19	128173	68.73	–55.65
0.06106	0.88690	13.68	128181	68.62	–54.91
0.07749	0.88809	14.09	128192	68.52	–54.27
0.09393	0.88928	14.48	128202	68.42	–53.69
0.11037	0.89047	14.82	128211	68.32	–53.16
LiClO ₄					
0.00000	0.88233	–	128148	69.02	–
0.02190	0.88411	28.37	128200	68.82	–69.23
0.04161	0.88569	28.91	128244	68.65	–67.64
0.05694	0.88692	29.25	128277	68.52	–66.57
0.07227	0.88813	29.54	128311	68.39	–65.86
0.08759	0.88935	29.78	128345	68.26	–65.09
0.10293	0.89055	30.04	128373	68.14	–64.40
LiBF ₄					
0.00000	0.88245	–	128146	69.01	–
0.01880	0.88380	24.89	128185	68.86	–61.32
0.03571	0.88500	25.50	128219	68.73	–60.07
0.04887	0.88591	25.87	128247	68.63	–59.30
0.06015	0.88670	26.15	128268	68.54	–58.72
0.07518	0.88774	26.50	128298	68.43	–58.03
0.09398	0.88903	26.86	128335	68.29	–57.25

Table 2. Limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_V^0) and experimental slopes (S_V) of lithium salts in tetrahydrofuran at 298.15 K

Salt	V_ϕ^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	S_V (cm ³ L ^{1/2} mol ^{-3/2})	σ	R^2
LiCl	8.720 ± 0.029	11.635 ± 0.11	0.059	0.999
LiBr	10.304 ± 0.018	13.616 ± 0.069	0.059	0.999
LiBF ₄	23.295 ± 0.011	11.651 ± 0.049	0.055	0.999
LiClO ₄	26.949 ± 0.016	9.616 ± 0.065	0.057	0.999

(ϕ_K) of the solution of LiCl, LiBr, LiBF₄ and LiClO₄ in THF at 298.15 K are given in Table 1.

From Table 1, it is seen that the sound velocity increases in concentration of the salt solution and these values are greater than that of the pure solvent. The limiting apparent molar adiabatic compressibilities (ϕ_K^0), were obtained by least squares plotting of $\phi_K - C$ data into the following equation,

$$\phi_K = \phi_K^0 + S_K \sqrt{C} \quad (5)$$

where S_K is the experimental slope.

The limiting apparent molar adiabatic compressibilities

(ϕ_K^0) and the experimental slope (S_K) along with the standard deviations are listed in Table 3. It is seen that ϕ_K^0 of LiCl, LiBr, LiBF₄ and LiClO₄ in THF at 298.15 K are found to be negative. The negative ϕ_K^0 values of these salts can be interpreted in terms of decrease of compressibility of the solvent THF.

Table 3. Limiting apparent molar isentropic compressibilities and the experimental slopes of the lithium salts in tetrahydrofuran at 298.15 K

Electrolyte	$10^{10} \phi_K^0$ (cm ³ mol ⁻¹ bar ⁻¹)	$10^{10} S_K$ (cm ³ mol ^{-3/2} kg ^{1/2} bar ⁻¹)	σ (%)
LiCl	-44.98	19.96	0.012
LiBr	-59.99	20.56	0.013
LiBF ₄	-64.61	24.00	0.014
LiClO ₄	-73.35	27.90	0.017

Experimental

Chemicals :

Tetrahydrofuran (Merck, India) was kept over KOH for several days and refluxed for 24 h and then distilled over LiAlH₄. The density and the viscosity of the purified solvent (0.882 g cm⁻³, 0.463 mPa.S at 298.15 K)^{6,7} agree well with the literature values⁸.

The salts were of Fluka's purum or puriss grade. Lithium chloride, lithium bromide and lithium tetrafluoroborate were dried under vacuum at high temperatures for 48 h and were used without further purification⁹. Lithium perchlorate was recrystallized three times from conductivity water and then dried under vacuum for several days⁹.

Apparatus and general procedure :

The densities were measured with an Ostwald-Sprengel type pycnometer¹⁰ having a bulb volume of about 25 cm³ and an internal diameter of capillary of about 1 mm. The pycnometer was calibrated at 298.15 K with doubly dis-

tilled water. Measurements were made using a single pan digital balance with an accuracy of ± 0.0001 g. The temperature of the thermostatic bath was controlled to ± 0.01 K of the desired temperature.

Sound velocities were measured with an uncertainty of $\pm 0.3\%$ using a single-crystal variable-path ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi, India) working at 4 MHz, which was calibrated with water, methanol and benzene¹¹. The temperature stability was maintained within ± 0.01 °C by circulating thermostated water around the measuring cell by a circulating pump.

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